

Research Paper

The Relationship between Demographic Characteristics and Academic Performance in English of Grade 11 Students

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ABSTRACT: The study entitled “The Relationship between Demographic Characteristics and Academic Performance in English of Grade 11 Students” aimed to seek the demographic characteristics of students and their academic performance and to determine if there is a significant relationship between demographic characteristics and academic performance in English of Grade 11 students. A descriptive-correlational research design was used in the study. The essential data were gathered from a sample size of 51 respondents using the validated modified demographic questionnaire. Data were analyzed and interpreted using frequency, percentage, and chi-square test as statistical tools. It was found that the academic performance of Grade 11 students in terms of grades was satisfactory. The result indicated that one (1) among four factors (Parent's Educational Attainment of Father) was significantly related to academic performance. Hence, based on these results, parents, especially fathers, should be knowledgeable enough about their children's academic needs. The researchers also suggested to future researchers the importance of conducting another study with other demographic characteristics not included in the study that may have a significant relationship to the student's academic performance.

KEYWORDS: Academic Performance, Demographic Characteristics, Parent's Educational Attainment, Grade 11 Students

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I. INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is one of the main expectations of students, teachers, and other educational stakeholders. As defined by examinations or ongoing evaluations, academic success is the extent to which students meet their short- and long-term educational goals (Collins (2007). Online and distant learning have been established amid the pandemic. At the same time, several factors, including demographics, the learning environment, work, income, etc., can affect a student's academic success, particularly in the modern day when education is primarily completed at home. Numerous empirical research, such as those by Ortega-Maldonado et al. (2017) and Brubacher and Silinda (2019), have shown that demographic factors, including gender, degree of study, and specialization, are significant factors in predicting students' academic success, which is in line with Tinto's (1975) theory.

Numerous studies on education have found that socio-demographic factors (such as gender, parent education level, and kind of school) can significantly impact pupils' academic achievement. For instance, in the United States, Urtel (2008) examined the variations in student academic performance between face-to-face and distance learning. The results showed a substantial connection between gender, student status, ethnicity, and academic achievement.

Andaya (2016) investigated the variables influencing the academic success of indigenous students at the Philippine Normal University-North Luzon. Andaya's research found that "instructional factors" significantly impacted the student's academic achievement. According to this, teachers must engage their pupils in "meaningful and authentic learning activities" to succeed in a class that supports knowledge creation. She

concluded that both students and teachers impacted academic performance but that it was ultimately up to the students to succeed or fail.

In addition, according to Manuel (2019), several educational research studies have revealed that socio-demographic characteristics (such as gender, parents' academic level, and type of school) can significantly influence the students' performance in chemistry. In this study, the gender, type of elementary school graduates, nature of commuting, and father and mother's educational attainment were identified as predictors of the Chemistry students' achievements. These attributes were employed to determine if there is a positive correlation with the Grade 9 students' performance in Chemistry at the Central University Laboratory High School (CMULHS) of S.Y. 2014-15.

This study assumed that students come from dynamic demographic characteristics that may influence their performance to excel in school differently. A local study showed a relationship between family income and parents' educational attainment. Hence, we conducted this study to determine the relationship between the two variables and whether demographic characteristics are related to the student's academic performance of the Grade 11 students of UMPC.

The study's primary goal is determining the association between student academic performance in Grade 11 at UM Peñaplata College and demographic factors. The study specifically looked for answers to the following questions: (1) What are the respondents' demographic characteristics in terms of their parents' socioeconomic situation, educational level, and gender? (2) How well do pupils succeed academically in terms of grades? (3) Does the academic performance of the students alter significantly when the following factors are taken into account: (a) the father's occupation; (b) the mother's occupation; (c) family income; (d) the father's educational attainment; (e) the mother's educational attainment; (f) gender? (4) Does demographic characteristics strongly correlate with students' academic achievement?

II. METHOD

Research Design

The research design refers to a chosen and planned way of investigating the social reality or the planned arrangement of how to address the research problem. It is organized in such a manner as to optimize research outcomes (Omari, 2011). The present study used a non-experimental, descriptive correlation design and quantitative research to implement further and finish the study. According to Kalla (2011), a correlation study determines whether or not two variables are correlated. It is to study whether an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase and decrease in the other variable. This means that this is a study of two or more variables from the same group of participants, and one is trying to determine if there is a relationship between the two variables. This is appropriate to the study since it will identify the relationship between demographic characteristics and students' academic performance.

Research Respondents

The researchers selected the demographic characteristics to determine its association with students' academic achievement. The UMPC has 61 Grade 11 students in the 2021–2022 academic year.

Furthermore, the study employed a simple random sampling by selecting a sample from the total population to make sure that the chosen sample was based on the population's characteristics and the study's objective. Based on the total population, the researchers randomly selected a sample size of 51, which was identified using the RAOSOFT calculator to generate or calculate the sample size. Through this sampling technique, it is plausible that the targeted respondents' characteristics are similar, which is related to the study's objective (Yang & Banamah, 2014). Hence, the study only surveyed respondents who were students of UM Peñaplata College.

Research Instruments

The sample size number of Grade 11 Senior High School students registered in UM Peñaplata College was gathered on the official record of the school's administration office to collect the relevant information from the responders. The researchers used a validated modified demographic questionnaire in a checklist format from the study of Agullana et al. (2017) to collect essential data relating to the study's goal. The researchers used the checklist format to collect crucial data about the study's purpose. The respondents could check their responses against the alternatives provided by the researchers using the distributed checklist. Students were also tasked to declare their average grades in the checklist. The researchers used five scoring categories: 90-100 as outstanding, 85-89 as very satisfactory, 80-84 as satisfactory, 75-79 as fairly satisfactory, and 75 and below as they did not meet expectations.

Research Procedure

The following procedures will be observed in gathering data.

1. *Ask permission to conduct the study.* The researchers wrote a letter for permission to the Director of the school to conduct a study on “The relationship between Demographic Characteristics and Student’s Academic Performance in English of Grade 11 in UM Peñaplata College” and also to the Senior High School Principal asking permission to gather of the Grade 11 student's grade.
2. *Questionnaire construction.* The researchers adapted a checklist format containing parents' socioeconomic status, educational attainment, and gender that would meet specific answers to acquire data for the study.
3. *Validation of questionnaire.* After the questionnaire was prepared, it was reviewed by the adviser and validated by the expert panel.
4. *Distribution of the questionnaire.* With the approval of the request, the researcher personally administered the distribution of Google form link questionnaires to the identified respondents through online communication applications, notably Messenger.
5. *Retrieval of the questionnaire.* Questionnaires were retrieved after having been accomplished by the respondents. This will be done on the respondents' convenient schedules.
6. *Collation and tabulation of the data.* The retrieved questionnaires were tallied, collated, and recorded accordingly. Results are analyzed. Interpret and statistically compute to answer the study question with the **statistician's assistance.**

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data analysis was done using frequency and percentage of demographic characteristics. At the same time, the mean was used to determine the level of academic performance of the Grade 11 students. The t-test assessed the significant difference between the student's academic performance regarding the demographic profile, specifically parents' educational attainment, family income, occupation, and gender. Pearson Chi-Square Test was the statistical measure used to test the hypothesis that a significant relationship exists between demographic characteristics and students' academic achievement.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the respondents' profiles regarding parents' educational attainment, occupation, family income, and student sex. Out of fifty-one (51) respondents, there are twenty-four (24), or 48.1% of fathers attained college; twenty (20), or 39.2 attained high school; five (5), or 9.8% attained elementary, and two (2) or 3.9% belong to others. There were twenty-five (25), or 49% of the mothers who attained college; twenty-one (21), or 41.2%, who attained high school, and five (5), or 9.8%, who attained elementary. While on the occupation of their parents, there are twenty-three (23), or 45.1% of the fathers belonged to blue-collar jobs, eighteen (18), or 35.3%, to white-collar jobs, and twenty-four (24), or 47.1%, belonged to others. There are seven (7), or 13.7 %, of the mothers whose work belongs to blue-collar jobs; twenty (20), or 39.2%, belong to white-collar jobs, and twenty-four (24), or 47.1%, belong to others. When it comes to family income, eight (8), or 15.7 percent have a 20,001 above family income; seven (7), or 13.7%, for 15,001 to 20,000; ten (10), or 19.6% for 10,001 to 15,000 and twenty-six (26) or 51% for 10,000 and below. Lastly, out of fifty-one (51) respondents, seventeen (17), or 33.3, are male, and thirty-four (34), or 66.7, are female.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Profile	N	%
Father’s Educational Attainment		
College	24	47.1
High School	20	39.2
Elementary	5	9.8
Others*	2	3.9
Mother’s Educational Attainment		
College	25	49.0
High School	21	41.2
Elementary	5	9.8
Father’s Occupation		
Blue Collar Jobs	23	45.1
White Collar Jobs	18	35.3
Others*	10	19.6
Mother’s Occupation		
Blue Collar Jobs	7	13.7
White Collar Jobs	20	39.2
Others	24	47.1

Family Income		
₱20,001-above	8	15.7
₱15,001-20,000	7	13.7
₱10,001-15,000	10	19.6
₱10,000 and below	26	51.0
Sex		
Male	17	33.3
Female	34	66.7

*Respondents indicated no father or not categorized to any characteristics stated

Level of Academic Performance of Students

In assessing the academic performance of the Grade 11 students, their Grades in English were indicated as the basis. The following table shows the result.

Table 2. Academic Performance of Students

Academic Performance	SD	M	Descriptive Equivalent
Transmuted Grade	6.41	83.02	Satisfactory

Based on the Department of Education grading system, all of the respondents passed the academe, which has a standard deviation of 6.41 and a mean score of 83.02 with a descriptive equivalent of satisfactory. Students at this level have developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understanding with a little guidance from the teacher and with peer assistance. Looking at the result, Grade 11 Senior High School students are doing well in their academic requirements and academic tests given to them by the institution.

According to Howse (1999), tests, exams, and instructor evaluations are routinely used to evaluate academic success. A study by Hammer (2003) showed that the achievement gap is not just a result of what occurs in the classroom. What occurs to them before and after school is what matters most. Parents and teachers have an essential role to play to ensure that every kid achieves excellent academic standards.

Significant Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when categorized according to its Demographic Characteristics

Table 3 shows the significant difference in student's academic performance in terms of father's educational attainment. Of 51 respondents, 24 fathers went to college, with a mean score of 84.17 and a standard deviation of 5.52. At the same time, 20 fathers went to high school with a mean score of 81.30 and a standard deviation of 6.77, and 5 fathers who attained elementary with a mean score of 82.20 and a standard deviation of 8.98 which resulted in a first value of 1.272 with a p-value of .295 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 and is not statistically significant. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in student's academic performance in terms of the educational achievement of their parents. This means that the student's educational achievement in terms of the father's learning and academic performance does not differ. Fathers, regarding their educational background, do not affect their children's academic achievement because fathers of the students have different viewpoints or attitudes regarding how they will value their children's education or academic success. This relates to the study by Mohammadi et al. (2016), which claimed that the difference in academic achievement between pupils in pre-high school, high school, and university was not caused by the father's degree of education.

Table 3. Significant Difference in the Academic Performance when Grouped According to Parent's Educational Attainment (Father)

Academic Performance	Elementary		High School		College		Others		F(3,47)	P	Decision on Ho
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Grade	82.20	8.98	81.30	6.77	84.17	5.52	88.50	2.12	1.272	.295	Accept

Table 4 shows the significant difference in student's academic performance regarding their mother's educational attainment. Of 51 respondents, 25 mothers went to college, with a mean score of 82.60 and a standard deviation of 6.22. In contrast, 21 mothers went to high school with a mean score of 84.57 and a standard deviation of 6.45, and 5 mothers who attained elementary with a mean score of 78.60 and a standard deviation of 5.94, which resulted in a first value of 1.928, with a p-value of .157 which is more significant than the significance level of 0.05 and is not statistically significant. This results in supporting the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in students' academic performance with respect to the parent's educational achievement. It means that students' academic performance in the era of mothers' educational achievement is the same. Regardless of their educational backgrounds, they have varied

perspectives or views regarding how they value their children's education. Hence, the mother's educational attainment was not a strong predictor of their children's academic success.

Oh-Hwang (1994) found that mothers' educational accomplishments were less crucial to their children's academic success. The results showed that mothers' educational achievement levels did not affect students' academic achievement. Thus, in this part, the table shows that there is no significant difference between students' academic performances in terms of their mother's educational attainment.

Table 4. Significant Difference in Academic Performance when Grouped According to Parent's Educational Attainment (Mother)

Academic Performance	Elementary		High School		College		F(2,48)	p	Decision on Ho
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Grade	78.60	5.94	84.57	6.45	82.60	6.22	1.928	.157	Accept

Table 5 reflects the significant difference in students' academic performance regarding their fathers' occupations. Out of 51 respondents, there are 23 fathers whose work belongs to blue-collar jobs, with a mean score of 83.26 and a standard deviation of 6.76. At the same time, there are 18 fathers whose work belongs to white-collar jobs with a mean score of 82.94 and a standard deviation of 5.98, which resulted in a F-value of 0.037 with a p-value of .963, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 and is not statistically significant. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in students' academic performance regarding their parents' occupations. It means the student's educational achievement regarding the father's occupation does not differ. This means that the father's profession is not a reliable indicator of the academic performance of the Grade 11 students. This illustrates that the students' fathers' occupations do not only matter if their work provides sufficient income to maintain their children's education.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Academic Performance when Grouped According to Parent's Occupation (Father)

Academic Performance	Blue Collar		White Collar		Others		F(2, 48)	P	Decision on Ho
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Grade	83.26	6.76	82.94	5.98	82.60	6.96	.037	.963	Accept

The result relates to Osuafor and Okonkwo's (2013) study conducted in Nigeria that found no significant relationship between parental occupation and students' achievement. Mainly because parents from different occupational classes frequently have varied parenting practices, methods for correcting their kids, and responses to their kids Ogunshola and Adewale (2012). Moreover, in the case of every family, these variations do not manifest themselves uniformly as expected (Rothstein, 2004).

Table 6 reflects the significant difference in students' academic performance in terms of mothers' occupations. Out of 51 respondents, seven mothers work in blue-collar jobs, with a mean score of 83.29 and a standard deviation of 5.53. At the same time, there are 20 mothers whose work belongs to white-collar jobs, with a mean score of 82.65 and a standard deviation of 6.70, and 24 mothers who belong to others, with a mean score of 83.25 and a standard deviation of 6.63, which resulted in a first value of 0.053 with a p-value of .949 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 and is not statistically significant. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in students' academic performance in terms of their parents' occupations. This means the mother's occupation is not a valid predictor of the student's academic success. This shows that as long as the dad's line of work earns them enough money to support their children's education, it does not matter what their mother's jobs are. Hence, students' educational achievement regarding the mother's occupation does not differ.

According to Ononuga (2005), a parent's socioeconomic standing and income are influenced by the type of work he or she does. The study of Ogunshola and Adewale (2012) disclosed that parental socioeconomic position had no appreciable influence on students' academic achievement. Heynes (1982) and Gottfried et al. (1988) could not demonstrate a difference in cognitive development between children with working moms and those with unemployed mothers. Furthermore, Rege et al. (2011) found in a Norwegian study that while the effect of female job loss is not statistically significant, the loss of a father's employment has a detrimental impact on a child's performance in school.

Table 6. Significant Difference in the Academic Performance when Grouped According to Parent’s Occupation (Mother)

Academic Performance	Blue Collar		White Collar		Others		F(2, 48)	P	Decision on Ho
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Grade	83.29	5.53	82.65	6.70	83.25	6.63	.053	.949	Accept

Table 7 reflects the significant difference in student's academic performance regarding their family income. Out of 51 respondents, 8 have a family income of 20,001 or above, with a mean score of 81.88 and a standard deviation of 7.43. At the same time, there are seven whose family income is 15,001 to 20,000 with a mean score of 80.86 and a standard deviation of 4.45; 10 of them have a family income of 10,001 to 15,000 with a mean score of 84.40 and a standard deviation of 6.22, and 26 students whose family income range from 10,000 and below with a mean score of 83.42 and a standard deviation of 6.73 which resulted in a first value of .524 with a p-value of .668 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05 and is not statistically significant. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in students' academic performance regarding their family income. This result comes with the ideology that students with varying family incomes each month can attain academic performance that is greater or lower. It is essential that their parents have the resources to support their kids' academic demands.

The findings are consistent with those of Jacob and Harvey's (2005) study, which found that while many students from high socioeconomic and intact households perform poorly academically, many students from low-income and single-parent homes excel academically. Students may also come from homes with highly educated parents who are actively involved in their kids' education but who struggle academically. A similar conclusion was reached by Hijazi and Naqvi (2006), who discovered that family income had no discernible influence on students' achievement. It implies that students from wealthier families need to place more value on their education.

Table 7. Significant Difference in Academic Performance when Grouped According to Family Income

Academic Performance	₱10,000 and below		₱10,001-15,000		₱15,001-20,000		₱20,001-above		F(2, 48)	p	Decision on Ho
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Grade	83.42	6.73	84.40	6.22	80.86	4.45	81.88	7.43	.524	.668	Accept

Table 8 shows the significant difference in students' academic performance regarding their sex. Out of 51 respondents, 17 of them are male with a mean score of 80.35 and a standard deviation of 4.97, and 34 of them are female with a mean score of 84.35 with a standard deviation of 6.69 which resulted in a t-value of 2.179 with a p-value of 0.34 which is less than the significance value of 0.05 and is statistically significant. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in student's academic performance in terms of their sex. This implies differences between males and females, meaning students' academic achievement depends on gender. Females may achieve higher academic success than males and vice versa. A gender gap consists of a barrier or hindrance to learning.

Table 8. Significant Difference in Academic Performance when Grouped According to Sex

Academic Performance	Male		Female		t(49)	p	Decision on Ho
	M	SD	M	SD			
Grade	80.35	4.97	84.35	6.69	2.179	.034	Reject

The result is consistent with research on adolescent mathematics achievement by Maccoby and Jackline (1974), which discovered that performance relies on both the respondents' genders. The study of gender differences in Kenya by Wamahiu (1992), which claims that boys and girls can have an equal degree of success motivation if both sexes are exposed to equal personal and situational circumstances, provides research support for this claim.

Significant Relationship between Demographic Characteristics and Student’s Academic Performance

The test of association of demographic characteristics and academic performance is shown in Table 9. The level of significance set for this study was $p < .05$.

Consequently, a close examination of the data further revealed that among the demographic characteristics, only the high educational attainment of the father got the high first value of 17.718 with a p-value of less than 0.05 and is significant to academic performance. Other characteristics such as parent's

occupation, family income, and sex do not significantly contribute to students' academic achievement. This implies that the father's educational attainment is the most significant predictor of the student's academic achievement among the demographic characteristics. This means that the higher the father's educational attainment, the higher the capacity to teach their children well. The less educated the father is, the less understanding they can give to help their children succeed academically. The rest of the domains, specifically the mother's educational attainment, parent's occupation, family income, and sex, do not significantly affect the student's academic performance. This signifies that a mother's educational attainment was not a strong predictor of their children's academic success since they have varied perspectives or views regarding how they value their education regardless of educational background. That parent's occupation is not a reliable indicator of the student's academic performance. Parent's occupation only matters if their work provides sufficient income to maintain their children's education. Students varying family incomes each month can attain academic performance that is greater or lower, and students may achieve the same or equal academic success as long as both sexes are exposed to equal personal and situational factors.

Table 9. Significant Relationship between the Demographic Characteristics and Student's Academic Performance

Demographic Characteristics	Academic Performance
	Grade
Parent's Education Attainment (Father)	17.718* (.039)
Parent's Education Attainment (Mother)	9.082 (.169)
Parent's Occupation (Father)	2.621 (.855)
Parent's Occupation (Mother)	1.139 (.980)
Family Income	6.561 (.683)
Sex	6.431 (.092)

$p^* < .05$

The above results concurred with the study of Oh-Hwang (1994), which discovered that while a mother's educational level has an indirect impact on children, a father's educational level has a direct one. According to his research, there was a substantial correlation between achievement and I.Q. scores in the American and Korean samples and the father's educational level. Other noteworthy findings included that children of men with more excellent educational backgrounds tended to be more innovative and academically successful. The study's findings suggested that children with highly educated fathers tend to accomplish at higher levels.

Likewise, the result is consistent with the study of Smith (1989), which compared the effects of maternal and paternal influences on kids' academic performance and educational ambitions and found that parental educational achievement significantly influenced students in the sixth, eighth, and tenth grades. The parents' educational background influenced the students' realistic expectations and ideal educational aspirations. According to the study's findings, parental education affects students' achievement. The result was similar to Hushak (1973), whose research conclusively showed that the father's educational level significantly impacted students' success. Parents with advanced degrees give their kids more or better-quality educational materials. The teacher is the most competent teaching input available to the child, regardless of the instructor's qualifications, and a child with less-educated parents does not have access to alternate skills teaching inputs. Other findings support the notion that the father's educational attainment is the main factor influencing the high standard of teaching input.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following were concluded:

The students' profiles show that most are females, and their parents attained college-level education. The white-collar job got the highest percentage regarding the mother's occupation. This means that most of the mothers work in government offices. On the family income, it was presented that 10,000 below got the highest percentage, which signifies that most family income is under the lowest ranges. In addition, the academic performance of the Grade 11 Senior High School students for the first semester is satisfactory. This means that

the students at this level have developed the basic knowledge, skills, and core understanding and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks with little teacher guidance and peer support. Since the results of the parent's educational attainment between the mother and father vary, parents of the students have different viewpoints or attitudes regarding how they will value their children's education or academic success based on their educational backgrounds. Lastly, the demographic characteristics regarding the parent's educational attainment of the father are positively significant, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the father's educational attainment affects the student's academic performance.

In light of the findings mentioned above and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were offered:

As a human institution, the school should also cater to the proper educational approach of teaching the students regardless of their demographic profile to increase their academic performance. This means that despite the student's socioeconomic background, gender, and parents' demographic profile, teachers should apply inclusivity and diversity to let their students feel comfortable and accepted.

Parents are recommended to thoroughly understand their kids' academic demands to give their kids the appropriate learning resources they need for school. Since parents' income has little to no bearing on their children's academic success, parents should be reminded to prioritize their children's education, regardless of their financial situation.

Since the study confirmed that there is no significant difference between students' academic performance and demographic characteristics in terms of mother's educational attainment, parent's occupation, family income, and sex, the researchers have recommended to future researchers that it is essential to conduct another study including other demographic characteristics not included in the study that may probably have a significant relationship to the academic performance of the students.

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